

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_3_3_2	
Title	<p>Enter the specific name of the tool or method. Use concise and clear titles to describe the tool.</p> <p>1KA online survey application (1KA is an abbreviation for "EnKlikAnketa", literally "One Click Survey")</p>
Category	<p>Economic/Socio-cultural/Environmental/Spatial</p> <p>Socio-cultural</p>
Purpose of the method	<p>Provide a brief explanation of the tool's purpose. What does it measure or analyse, and in what context is it applied?</p> <p>1KA is an open source application that enables services for online surveys. It allows users to make different surveys, forms or voting questionnaires with many options for question types, IF conditions, loops, statistical analyses etc. It allows collection and analysis of survey answers.</p>
Effort in time	<p>Please estimate the time required for the method. How long does it take until results are available?</p> <p>Few months</p>
Number of objects investigated	<p>If this applies to your method, please estimate the number of objects or measurements.</p> <p>=Number of participants; approximately 100</p>
Data format	<p>Indicate the format of the data collected (e.g., numerical, qualitative, geospatial, textual, images).</p>
Description	<p>Write a brief description of the tool. Explain how it works, the variables it measures, and how the results can be interpreted</p> <p>1KA is an open-source application for online surveys developed at the Centre for Social Informatics, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana. The application provides functionalities for questionnaire creation (design and technical setup), survey implementation (invitations, publishing, and data collection), and data analysis (including paradata).</p> <p>1KA emphasizes simplicity by minimizing clicks, as reflected in its name "EnKlikAnketa" (translated as "One Click Survey"). It supports unlimited free use for online surveys, while additional services such as training, custom installations, or data analysis are available for a non-profit fee. The application can be installed on any server, linked via API, or used offline for personal interviews (CAPI) on Windows devices. It is completely in accordance to legal request for data protection.</p>

Basic Literature	<p>List key references related to the tool, formatted in APA style. Include relevant articles, books, or reports that explain or document its use.</p> <p>/</p>
Contact person within the project	<p>Provide the contact information for the person responsible for the tool within the project (name, email, and, if relevant, their role in the project team)</p> <p>Dr. Elena Bužan, elena.buzan@upr.si, project leader</p> <p>Luka Duniš, luka.dunis@upr.si</p> <p>Dr. Žiga Velkavrh, ziga.velkavrh@upr.si</p> <p>Lan Zirkelbach, lan.zirkelbach@upr.si</p>
Linked material	<p>Link any relevant materials such as questionnaires, digital tools, tutorials, or datasets. Use direct links or indicate where these materials can be accessed (e.g., a shared project folder).</p> <p>https://www.1ka.si/d/en/about/general-description</p> <p>https://1ka.arnes.si/a/442cc376&preview=on&testdata=on</p>